

Scientific Note

First records of *Phorticus collaris* Stål, 1873 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Nabidae) in Costa Rica, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Panama with notes on its distribution range

Damsel bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Nabidae) are smaller, rarely larger than 10 mm, active predators found in plant litter and on the plants themselves. They are general predators, feeding on a wide range of smaller insects and other arthropods and are sometimes considered important elements of a biological control program (Saito et al. 2023). Lattin (1989) provided a detailed review of family including biological and life history information. Henry & Lattin (1988) cataloged the damsel bugs of Canada and the continental United States, while Volpi & Coscarón. (2010) cataloged the Neotropical species.

Phorticus collaris Stål, 1873 is a small (~3 mm), damsel bug (Fig. 1 A, B, C) described from Texas (Stål 1873, Harris 1929, Kerzher & Henry 2008). Blinn (1996) extended the distribution range of *P. collaris* to include the southeastern U.S.A., recording two specimens that he collected over four years at lights in North Carolina. He also lists specimens from Tennessee and additional records from locations in Texas. Blinn (1996) provided a redescription of the species along with a very nice line drawing. Henry and Brambila (2003) provided the first records from Florida based on a female taken at lights in Leon County. Tumilson & Chordas (2018) provide a record for Arkansas and refer to BugGuide records from Oklahoma and South Carolina. Bugguide (2025) posts specimen data in Texas Oklahoma, Louisiana, and South Carolina, and GBIF (2025) lists specimens from Arkansas, Louisiana, Oklahoma, Tennessee, and Texas. We have not viewed the specimens from any of these postings but, given the distinctive morphology of the species and geographic relationships to verified localities, believe them to be accurate.

Figure 1. *Phorticus collaris* from Guatemala with its label: A. general habitus, dorsal view; B. general habitus, lateral view; C. head, cranial view.

On the other hand, *P. collaris* has a scattered known distribution in Central and South America. Champion (1899) was the first to record the species from Mexico (Teapa, Tabasco State). Henry & Lattin (1988) and Volpi & Coscarón. (2010) also list the species from Mexico. Texas A&M University has specimens from Veracruz and Tamaulipas, Mexico (M. Cupello, personal communication) and Panama (**new country record**) (GBIF 2025); the USNM has several specimens from Mexico and others intercepted at U.S. ports of entry originating from Mexico (J. Zahniser, personal communication). Froeschner (1981) reported a single female from Ecuador. Brailovsky (2018) recorded *P. collaris* from Honduras. Although Maes (1998) did not list it as occurring in Nicaragua, Harry Brailovsky (UNAM, personal communication) provided a record from Jinotega, Nicaragua (**new country record**). The U.S. National Museum has one female specimen from Costa Rica (Los Ríos, Quevedo, 11 May 1975) (J. Zahniser, personal communication) (**new country record**). Carpintero et al. (2006) recorded *P. collaris* from Argentina (Buenos Aires, Verónica, Punta Indio), with additional records from the U.S.A., Mexico, and Ecuador. Thus, the currently known distribution of *P. collaris* extends from a northern limit in the U.S.A., which includes Arkansas, Oklahoma, Tennessee, and North Carolina, to Panama in Central America and Argentina in South America. It is expected to be found in other Central and South American countries.

Harris (1929) stated that nothing was known of the species habitats except that it was found on the ground. The fact that virtually all specimens were taken at lights may limit the number of specimens in collections, as one would not normally think of a primary method of collecting damsel bugs as at lights. For example, Texas A&M University (M. Cupello, personal communication) provided information on 68 specimens in their collection; 15 have no collection method, one was taken in a yellow pan-trap, and 52 were taken at lights. The fact that the species is small (~3 mm) may further limit its collection at lights. In Guatemala, all our specimens were collected at lights. We assume that specimens are normally located in leaf litter, on the soil surface, or in vegetation where they are preying on other arthropods, but this needs to be verified by the collection of live individuals in these or other habitats.

In Guatemala, we found the species widespread at lower elevations (43–627 m), though not abundant at any individual site. While we collected at many higher elevation sites (up to 3000 m), we collected no specimens at any of these higher elevations. It is not known if the species is restricted to lower elevations or if this is a collecting artifact. All sites were open or sparsely forested.

Figure 2 is a map of collection locations in Guatemala and Central America; the map was developed using Simplemappr (Simplemappr.net).

Repository collections for insect specimens are abbreviated as follows:

TAMU	Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas
UNAM	Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México City, México
USNM	United States National Museum, Washington, D.C.
UVGC	Universidad del Valle de Guatemala, Guatemala City, Guatemala
WSUC	Washington State University, Pullman, Washington

GUATEMALA: Alta Verapaz Department: Monumento Natural Semuc Champey, ~9 km SE of Lanquín, 15.53646°N 89.95522°W, 260 m, 3 Dec 2021, lights (2, WSUC; 1, UVGC): Baja Verapaz Department: “Mi Rancho” Aldea Concuá, Granados, along Río Motagua, 14.87439°N 90.59035°W, 627 m, 17 Nov 2022, lights

Figure 2. Distribution map of *Phorticus collaris* in Central America. Stars indicate capital city of country for reference: 1–9 Guatemala: 1. Monumento Natural Semuc Champey, Alta Verapaz; 2. Mi Rancho, Aldea Concuá, Baja Verapaz; 3. Finca Bello Horizonte, Livingston, Lanquín, Izabal; 4. El Rosario National Park, Sayaxché, Petén; 5. Ixpanpajul Natural Reserve, Santa Ana, Petén; 6. Yaxhá National Park, Flores, Petén; 7. Petencito, Flores, Petén; 8. El Bosque, Machaquilá, Petén; 9. Erhco Park, Chiquimulilla, Santa Rosa; Number 10. Nicaragua, Zelaya Department; Number 11. Costa Rica, Guanacaste Province; Number 12. Panama, Colón Province.

(3, WSUC; 1, UVGC): Izabal Department: Finca Bello Horizonte ~8 km SE of Río Dulce, 15.59252°N 88.94366°W, 43 m, 11 Mar 2017 (1, WSUC): Petén Department: Parque Nacional El Rosario, E of Sayaxché, 16.52414°N 90.16009°W, 30 June 2014 (3, WSUC); Parque Natural Ixpanpajul, Rt. CA-13, near Santa Ana, 16.87341°N 89.81496°W, 17–18 Oct 2017 (1, WSUC); Parque Natural Ixpanpajul, Rt. CA-13, near Santa Ana, 16.87027°N 89.82330°W, 6 June 2016 (1, WSUC); Parque Nacional Yaxhá, ENE of El Remate, 17.06722°N 89.40020°W, 167 m, 13 Mar 2017 (3, WSUC); Zoológico Petencito near Santa Elena, 16.92780°N 89.86671°W, 100 m, 5 Dec 2021, (3, WSUC; 2, UVGC); Balneario El Bosque along Río Machaquilá, ~9 km E of Machaquilá, 16.39023°N 89.51188°W, 390 m, 6 Dec 2021 (3, WSUC; 2, UVGC): Santa Rosa Department: Rt. 16, Parque Ecológico del Sur, “Erhco Park”, Chiquimulilla, 14°06.633'N 90°22.294'W 350 m, 9 June 2011 (1, WSUC).

Costa Rica: 10 mi NW of Liberia, blacklight at Río Ahogados, 25 July 1965 (1, USNM).

Nicaragua: Jinotega, P. N. Cerro Saslaya, 1040 m, 13.76770°N, 85.02431°W, 12 May 2011 (1, UNAM).

Panama: Colón Province, 3 km S of Sabanitas (no date) (1, TAMU GBIF).

Acknowledgments. We want to thank Mario Cupello (Texas A&M University), James Zahniser (USNM), Susan Halbert (Florida State Collection of Arthropods), and Harry Brailovsky (UNAM) for their support in providing information on specimens under their care. Tom Henry verified our initial identification. We would also like to thank the Centro de Estudios Ambientales y Biodiversidad (Universidad del Valle de Guatemala) for support, especially Daniel Ariano. CONAP (Consejo Nacional de Áreas Protegidas) has always supported our efforts with research and export permits (current research license DVCB-16-2024).

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Received 28 Aug 2025; accepted 8 Nov 2025. Publication date 31 December 2025

Subject editor Michael Forthman